

ENDOMETRIAL PATHOLOGIES IN MENSTRUAL IRREGULARITIES: A PRE- AND POST-COVID-19 COMPARATIVE STUDY

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Keywords

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ABSTRACT

To compare endometrial pathologies in patients with menstrual irregularity before and after the COVID-19 pandemic. This cross-sectional study examined 140 patients before COVID-19 and 150 patients after COVID-19 who presented with menstrual irregularity. Endometrial thickness values, hysteroscopy findings, and pathology results were recorded via transvaginal ultrasonography (USG) between days 3-6 of menstruation. Patients receiving hormone replacement therapy (HRT), having a positive COVID-19 test, systemic disease, using an intrauterine device, having fluid accumulation in the endometrial cavity, or having non-endometrial pathologies that could cause bleeding were excluded. Pathology results included proliferative endometrium, endometrial polyp, secretory endometrium, endometritis, atrophic endometrium, hyperplasia, myoma, drug-induced endometrium, and endometrial cancer. There was a statistically significant decrease in the number of proliferative endometrium cases after COVID-19 ($p < 0.05$) and a statistically significant increase in the number of endometrial polyps ($p < 0.05$). Following the COVID-19 pandemic, there was a noticeable reduction in proliferative endometrium and an increase in endometrial polyp incidence among patients with menstrual irregularity. These findings suggest that COVID-19 may have an impact on endometrial pathology, warranting further investigation.

INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic, driven by the novel coronavirus SARS-CoV-2, has had extensive and varied impacts on global health, affecting not only those infected but also those managing chronic health conditions¹. While the primary focus has been on respiratory complications, there is growing interest in understanding how COVID-19 affects other systems, including the female reproductive system².

Menstrual irregularities are a common gynecological issue, often indicative of underlying hormonal imbalances, systemic health conditions, or endometrial pathology. The endometrium, the inner lining of the uterus, is highly responsive to hormonal changes and can exhibit a range of pathological conditions such as hyperplasia, polyps, and inflammation, which can disrupt normal menstrual cycles. Understanding the factors that influence endometrial pathology is crucial for diagnosing and treating menstrual irregularities³. Emerging research suggests that COVID-19 may have direct and indirect effects on menstrual health. One proposed mechanism is the disruption of the hypothalamic-pituitary-ovarian (HPO) axis due to the systemic inflammatory response triggered by SARS-CoV-2 infection. This inflammation can alter the secretion of gonadotropin-releasing hormone (GnRH) and subsequent hormone levels, potentially leading to menstrual irregularities⁴. Additionally, the presence of ACE2 receptors in the ovaries and endometrium implies that SARS-CoV-2 could directly affect these tissues, impacting their function and contributing to pathological changes⁵.

Furthermore, the stress and lifestyle changes induced by the pandemic, such as altered physical activity, diet, and mental health challenges, may also influence menstrual health. Psychological stress is known to affect the menstrual cycle through various pathways, including the HPO axis⁶. The healthcare disruptions caused by the pandemic, including delays in routine gynecological care, may have compounded these effects, making it essential to investigate these potential connections comprehensively.

Several studies have begun to explore these associations. For instance, a study by Ding et al. observed an increase in menstrual irregularities among women who had recovered from COVID-19⁷. Another study by Lebar et al. found that women reported changes in their menstrual patterns,

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including frequency and flow, during the pandemic period, suggesting a possible link to both the infection and the psychosocial impacts of the pandemic⁸. This study seeks to expand on this emerging body of knowledge by examining endometrial pathological findings in patients with menstrual irregularities before and after the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic. By comparing endometrial biopsy results and clinical data, we aim to elucidate whether there is a significant correlation between COVID-19 infection and changes in endometrial pathology. This research is critical for developing targeted strategies to manage menstrual health in the context of ongoing and future pandemics, ensuring that women receive comprehensive and informed gynecological care.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study was to investigate the relationship between covid 19 virus and endometrial pathologies in a cross-sectional study conducted at Sivas Cumhuriyet University Hospital. The study was approved by Cumhuriyet University Human Research Ethics Committee (Registry No:2023-09/32). The data of 290 patients who underwent hysteroscopy with the diagnosis of menstrual irregularity in our clinic between 2014 and 2023 were obtained retrospectively.

Demographic information was collected for both patients with after covid and patients with before covid patients. The demographic characteristics included " age, body mass index (BMI), pregnancy history, parity, abortion history, and gynecological history, physical and pelvic examination findings, transvaginal ultrasonography (USG), findings, endometrial thickness, hysteroscopy findings, and pathology results".

Pregnant women, patients with systemic diseases, using intrauterine devices, fluid detected in the endometrial cavity, patients taking HRT, and patients with pathological examination findings who had menstrual irregularities were excluded from the study.

Histopathological analysis of endometrial tissue samples was performed to identify various pathologies, including proliferative endometrium, endometrial polyps, secretory endometrium, endometritis, atrophic endometrium, hyperplasia, myoma, endometrial carcinoma and drug-induced endometrium.

Statistical analysis

IBM SPSS Statistics 22.0 (IBM Corp. Released 2013. IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows, Version 22.0. Armonk, NY: IBM Corp.) program was used. The conformity of numerical variables to normal distribution was analysed by Kolmogorov-Smirnov ($n \geq 50$) tests. Numerical variables were given as

mean, standard deviation and median (min-max). The comparison of the numerical variables between two groups was performed by Independent Samples T test when the normal distribution was appropriate and Mann-Whitney U test when the normal distribution was not appropriate. Chi-Square test was used in the evaluation of the data. Values were expressed as number and percentage of individuals and the error level was taken as 0.05. Categorical variables were given as number and percentage. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered significant.

RESULTS

All the patients who enrolled in the study completed the procedures. Among the 290 women who participated in our study, 140 experienced patients with before covid, while 150 patients with after covid. Demographic factors such as BMI, gestational age, gravidity, parity, abortion, D&C (dilation&curettage) showed no significant differences between the patients with before covid and patients with after covid groups ($p > 0.05$) The age and endometrial thickness of patients with after covid were significantly higher than those of the patients with before covid group ($p < 0.05$) (**Table 1**).

Pathology results like secretory endometrium, endometritis, atrophic endometrium, hyperplasia, myoma, endometrial carcinoma, endometrium under drug effect did not differ significantly between the groups ($p > 0.05$).

In the patients with after covid group, endometrial polyp were higher than those of the patients with before covid group, in contrast, patients with after covid exhibited significant lower in proliferative endometrium compared to the patients with before covid group ($p < 0.05$).

DISCUSSION

Our study examined the endometrial pathological findings of patients presenting with menstrual irregularities before and after the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic. The results revealed a statistically significant decrease in the number of cases of proliferative endometrium and a significant increase in the incidence of endometrial polyps in the post-COVID cohort.

The observed decrease in proliferative endometrium could be attributed to several factors associated with the physiological and psychological impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic. Stress and anxiety, which have been markedly elevated during the pandemic, can disrupt the hypothalamic-pituitary-ovarian (HPO) axis, leading to alterations in menstrual cycles and endometrial pathology. Additionally, changes in lifestyle, including variations in diet, physical activity, and weight gain, might have influenced hormonal balance and menstrual regularity, thereby affecting endometrial proliferation^{4,9}.

Table 1. Demographic parameters and pathology findings of study groups.

	Before COVID-19	After COVID-19	p
	(n=150)	(n=140)	
Age (y)	43.6± 9.6	41.0± 6.8	<0.05*
BMI(kg/m ²)	28.7±5.7	28.8±8.0	>0.05
Pregnancy history		3.0 (0-7)	
Gravidity (number)	3.0 (0-9)	3.0 (0-7)	>0.05
Parity (number)	3.0 (0-7)	0.0 (0-3)	>0.05
Abortion (number)	0.0 (0-3)	0.0 (0-3)	>0.05
dilation curettage	0.0 (0-3)		>0.05
D&C(number)			
Endometrial thickness(number)	9.8± 4.0	8.5± 3.9	<0.05*
Pathology findings		57(40.7%)	
Proliferative endometrium	35 (23.5%)	37(26.4%)	<0.05*
Endometrial polyp	80(53.7%)	18(12.9%)	<0.05*
Secretory endometrium	20(13.4%)	13(9.3%)	>0.05
Endometritis	1 (0.7%)	5(3.6%)	>0.05
Atrophic endometrium	0(0.0%)	3(2.1%)	---
Hyperplasia	6(4.0%)	2(1.4%)	>0.05
Myoma	5(3.4%)	0(0.0%)	>0.05
Endometrial carcinoma	2(1.3%)	1(0.7%)	--
Drug-induced endometrium	0(0.0%)		--

Data were presented as mean ± SD, median (min-max) and percentage as appropriate. D&C, dilation& curettage. Bold values are statistically significant (*p<0.05)

On the other hand, the significant increase in the incidence of endometrial polyps post-COVID warrants a closer examination of the underlying mechanisms. COVID-19 has been associated with a hyperinflammatory state and endothelial dysfunction, which could potentially contribute to the development of endometrial polyps. The virus's ability to induce widespread systemic inflammation may affect endometrial tissue, promoting polyp formation. Furthermore, changes in medical care access and utilization during the pandemic may have led to delayed diagnoses and treatments, possibly contributing to the observed increase in endometrial polyps^{9,10}. Our findings align with emerging literature suggesting that COVID-19 can impact menstrual health and gynecological conditions. For instance, a study by Błażejewska et al. reported menstrual changes in women with COVID-19, highlighting the virus's potential effects on reproductive health¹¹. Similarly, Nepomnaschy et al. documented an increase in gynecological issues among women during the pandemic, further supporting our observations¹². It is also essential to consider the role of direct viral effects on the endometrium. SARS-CoV-2, the virus causing COVID-19, has been detected in various body tissues, including the female reproductive tract. While direct infection of endometrial tissue by the virus remains speculative, it raises questions about potential localized inflammatory responses contributing to changes in endometrial pathology^{3,10,13}. Our study underscores the need for heightened awareness and monitoring of menstrual and endometrial health in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic. Healthcare providers should be

vigilant in assessing menstrual irregularities and endometrial changes in patients with a history of COVID-19 or those affected by the pandemic's broader health implications. Further research is warranted to elucidate the precise mechanisms driving these pathological changes and to develop targeted interventions to mitigate the pandemic's impact on women's reproductive health. A limitation of our study sample size may be limited, reducing the generalizability of the findings. Additionally, various confounding factors, such as stress, changes in lifestyle, and other health conditions, may also contribute to menstrual irregularities. Isolating the impact of Covid-19 from these factors can be challenging. The severity of Covid-19 infection were not uniformly accounted for, which could influence the extent of menstrual irregularities observed.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the significant decrease in proliferative endometrium and the increase in endometrial polyps post-COVID highlight the pandemic's complex influence on gynecological health. Understanding these changes is crucial for developing effective clinical strategies to support women's reproductive health during and after the COVID-19 pandemic.

Conflict of interest

No conflict of interest is reported by the authors.

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No

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